

iQonic

IQONIC

Innovative strategies, sensing and process chains for increased
**Quality, re-configurability, and recyclability of Manufacturing
Optoelectronics**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY / ABSTRACT

In this report we discuss optical systems, their properties and the parameters that influence their characteristics and performance. The first part gives an overview over four categories of optical systems: Waveguiding systems, free-space optical systems, illumination systems and imaging systems. Main properties and primary and secondary parameters, where applicable, are discussed and listed in specific tables. Then, applications of the four use case partners are discussed together with threshold values for the relevant parameters.

2 Introduction

Optical systems are used in a vast number of applications/products covering all aspects of our everyday life. Each application requires different types of optics, light sources and other functionalities. We split the optical applications in four categories: Waveguiding systems, free-space systems, illumination systems and imaging systems. The different requirements in terms of optoelectrical functionalities are presented in the following sections and tables. At the end we discuss how these functionalities relate to the products fabricated at the iQonic use case partners.

3 Waveguiding systems

3.1 Overview

In general, electromagnetic radiation can propagate through free-space but it can be also guided in structures like waveguides. The classification of optical waveguides is done according to various physical aspects:

- Material (glass, polymer, semiconductor, dielectrics)
- Geometry (planar, strip, fiber, ...)
- Mode structure (single-mode, multi-mode)
- Refractive index distribution (step, gradient index)

Examples for optical waveguides are optical fibers and dielectric waveguides made of plastic and glass, with the most prominent application the worlds telecommunication infrastructure that relies heavily on fiber communication systems, from interconnects in data centers to overseas cables.

3.2 Optical fibers

An optical fiber is a cylindrical waveguide that transmits light along its longitudinal axis. It consists of a core made of dielectric material (typically silica glass) with a higher refractive index that is surrounded by a cladding layer that is made of dielectric material with lower refractive index. The refractive index variations in the material are typically obtained by adding dopants with refractive index profiles that can be abrupt (step-index fiber), gradual (graded-index fiber) or of more complex shape. Fibers with core diameters typically smaller than 10 μ m are called single-mode fibers because they support only a single optical mode with two polarization states, whereas multi-mode fibers with larger diameters guide multiple modes.

The light is transported in the fiber by total internal reflection, only if certain conditions on the angle of the incident beam are met. This is called the acceptance cone of the fiber and the sine of the maximum angle is called the numerical aperture (NA). The larger the numerical aperture of the fiber the easier it is to couple light into it with single-mode fibers having small numerical aperture. With the advancement of fiber drawing technology, a new type of micro structured optical fibers have been introduced where the refractive index variation is arranged in a regular pattern. In these photonic crystal fibers (PCF) effects of light diffraction assist or replace the mechanism of total reflection to confine and guide the light in the fiber and allow to tailor further the properties of the fiber or the transmitted light. These fibers have highly specialized applications, including transmission of high power beams.

Loss is a critical parameter for optical fibers. There are two major mechanisms that contribute to the loss in optical fibers: Material absorption and Rayleigh scattering. Both depend on the wavelength of the transported light and in silica glass fibers a minimum is obtained at about 1.55 μ m wavelength. Absorption is highly dependent on impurities and therefore ultra-pure base material has to be used for the fiber fabrication. The attenuation of such fibers is typically below 0.2 dB/km at

1.55 μm whereas the lowest reported attenuation of solid core photonic crystal fiber is 0.37 dB/km¹, and for hollow core is 1.2 dB/km². Optical fibers based on plastic have much higher attenuation coefficients around 1 dB/m.

As discussed above, the refractive index of the silica glass base material can be lowered and raised by adding dopants. If certain rare-earth elements such as erbium are added as dopant, the fiber becomes an active material that can be used for fiber amplifiers and lasers.

In summary, the most prominent parameters to characterize an optical fiber are:

- Material
- Mode acceptance (single- or multi-mode)
- Type (step-index, graded-index, photonic crystal fiber, ...)
- Fiber loss / amplification
- Wavelength dispersion

Fibers are coupled together by splicing the end of each fiber in a way that the surface is perfectly flat and clean. Then the two fiber ends are carefully aligned to each other and fixed either by fusing the silica glass or mechanically holding and stabilizing the fibers. There exist also various set of connectors that allow to connect fibers more conveniently. Each fiber interface will add additional losses and contribute to the overall attenuation of the complete system.

3.2.1 Free-space coupling

In order to couple light into or out of the fiber and interface it with other elements like laser diodes, detectors, modulators, photonic integrated circuits (PIC) or free-space optics, fibers are tapered or lensed and / or combined with a lens to allow coupling over an air gap. The tapering / lensing is performed using polishing, laser cutting or fusion splicing and allows to match the optical mode into the fiber with the one in the facing element. For coupling over an air gap, aspheric lenses with high numerical aperture (NA) are typically used in order to maximize coupling efficiency and minimize aberrations. Coupling is never perfect with maximal coupling efficiencies in the order of 70-80%.

The table below presents a summary of parameters related to waveguiding systems, in particular fiber optical systems:

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Description	Measurement method(s)
Optical fibers				
Material	-	-	Material of the fiber core and the cladding	(Property)
Type	-	-	Type of the refractive profile, i.e. step-index, graded-index, PCF, ...	(Property)
Mode acceptance	-	-	Whether the single accepts one single optical mode or multi-mode	(Property)
Fiber loss	α	dB/km	Fiber loss	Power meter
Fiber dispersion	D	ps/nm/km	Fiber dispersion	Wavemeter
Numerical aperture	NA	[]	Numerical aperture	(Property)

¹ Tajima K, Zhou J, Nakajima K, Sato K (2004). "Ultralow Loss and Long Length Photonic Crystal Fiber" *Journal of Lightwave Technology*. *Journal of Lightwave Technology*. **22**: 7–10

²P. Roberts, F. Couny, H. Sabert, B. Mangan, D. Williams, L. Farr, M. Mason, A. Tomlinson, T. Birks, J. Knight, and P. St. J. Russell, "Ultimate low loss of hollow-core photonic crystal fibres," *Opt. Express* 13, 236-244 (2005)

Tapering	-	-	Whether the ends of the fiber are tapered or lensed for optimization of optical interface	(Property)
Fiber-coupled systems				
Coupling efficiency	η	%	Relative power that is coupled into the fiber	Power meter
Secondary parameters				
Vibration sensitivity	-	-	Coupling vs. vibrations	Shaker
Temperature sensitivity	-	-	Coupling vs. temperature changes	Environmental chamber

4 Free-space systems

4.1 Overview

In this section, we discuss the functionalities of free-space coupled laser systems. Such systems range from small systems assembled in micro-optics, like for example a LIDAR range sensor or a laser diode whose emission is coupled into a fiber using an aspheric lens (see section 3.2.1), to extremely complex systems based on thousands of discrete optical elements mounted on large optical tables³. We divided the parameters into three broad categories: mode of operation and optical power (Section 4.2.1), spatial parameters (Section 4.2.2), which include all the geometric and propagation properties of the beam, and spectral parameters (Section 4.2.3), which include the spectral properties.

4.2 Beam parameters

4.2.1 Mode of operation and optical power

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Description	Measurement method(s)
Mode of operation		-	Pulsed or continuous-wave	Not measured. Achieved by design and specified by the manufacturer.
Continuous-wave lasers				
Continuous-wave optical power	P	W	Total optical power carrier by the beam.	Calibrated photodetector
Relative power stability	$\Delta P/P$	%	Relative power fluctuation over a given time duration. Typically, the rms value is given.	Photodetector
Pulsed lasers				
Pulsed repetition frequency	PRF	Hz	Frequency at which the laser is pulsed	Capture optical waveform with a fast detector
Pulse width	PW	s	Duration of the optical pulse	Capture optical waveform with

³ As an example we would like to mention the « Bivoj » super laser that we were able to visit during our last iQonic meeting at HiLASE facilities.

				a fast detector
Duty cycle	DCc	%	= PRF * PW Fraction of the time during which the laser is ON	Usually calculated, not measured
Average optical power	P _{av}	W	Total optical power carried by the beam averaged over many pulses.	Calibrated photodetector with a response time smaller than the pulse repetition period
Peak optical power	P _{pk}	W	Optical power during the pulses	Can be calculated from average power and duty cycle or measured with a fast, calibrated photodetector (not common)
Relative average power stability	$\Delta P_{av}/P_{av}$	%	Relative average power fluctuation over a given time duration. Typically, the rms value is given.	Photodetector
Relative pulse-to-pulse power fluctuation	$\Delta P_{pk}/P_{pk}$	%	Relative fluctuation of peak power between pulses.	Fast photodetector

4.2.2 Spatial parameters

In the following, we assume paraxial propagation along the optical axis z with the laser source located at $z = 0$.

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Description	Measurement method(s)
Near field beam diameters	$2w_x$ $2w_y$	mm	Diameters of the beam along the two axes transverse axes to the beam propagation (x and y)	Beam profiler, e.g. 2D detector array (imager). According to the international standard ISO 11146, the D4 σ method should be used to calculate the beam diameter from the measured intensity profile.
Far field beam divergence	$2\theta_{0,x}$ $2\theta_{0,y}$	mRad	Beam divergence (full angle) at a distance $\gg z_R$ from the beam waist location.	Measurement of beam diameter as function of position for $z - z_0 \gg z_R$.
Beam waist diameters or spot size	$2w_{0,x}$ $2w_{0,y}$	mm	Minimum value of the beam diameter along the propagation axis	Beam profiler moving along the optical axis.
Beam waist location	$z_{0,x}$ $z_{0,y}$	mm	Position along the z axis at which the beam diameter is the smallest.	Beam profiler moving along the optical axis.
Rayleigh range	$z_{R,x}$ $z_{R,y}$	mm	Range over which the beam diameter is $\leq \sqrt{2} w_0$	Beam profiler moving along the optical axis.
Beam pointing error	α_x α_y	mRad	Angle between the beam direction and the optical axis z . The optical axis is defined by mechanical references on the laser package, e.g. holes for	Beam profiler plus mechanical or optical reference.

			location pins.	
Beam pointing stability	$\Delta\alpha_x$ $\Delta\alpha_y$	mRad	Variation of beam pointing stability over a given time duration.	Beam profiler.
Beam parameter product	BPP	mm*mrad	Product of beam waist radius times beam divergence (half angle). It is always $\geq \lambda/\pi$. The minimum value is achieved for a fundamental (TEM ₀₀) Gaussian beam	Calculated from measurements of beam waist diameter and beam divergence according to ISO 11146 test methods
Beam propagation factor	M^2	-	Unitless parameter ≥ 1 quantifying the beam quality defined as $M^2 = \pi *BPP/\lambda$. The minimum value is achieved for a fundamental (TEM ₀₀) Gaussian beam	Calculated from measurements of beam waist diameter and beam divergence according to ISO 11146 test methods

4.2.3 Spectral parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Description	Measurement method(s)
Spectrum type		-	Single-mode or multimode	Spectrometer, e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - optical spectrum analyzer - Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer - grating spectrometer - etc.
Multimode Lasers				
Center frequency	ν_c	Hz	Center of mass of the multimode spectrum	Calculated from emission spectrum measured with a spectrometer
Spectral width	$\Delta\nu$	Hz	Spectral width of the multimode spectrum	Calculated from emission spectrum measured with a spectrometer
Mode spacing	$\Delta\nu_{FSR}$	Hz	Frequency spacing between two consecutive modes.	Calculated from emission spectrum measured with a spectrometer or electrical measurement of intermode beat note
Mode linewidth	$\delta\nu$	Hz	Spectral width of one line of the multimode spectrum over a given time duration. Typically defined as the full width at half maximum (FWHM).	High resolution spectrometer
Single mode Lasers				
Emission frequency	ν		Center of the spectral line	Spectrometer
Linewidth	$\delta\nu$	Hz	Spectral width of the	High resolution spectrometer

			emission line over a given time duration. Typically defined as the full width at half maximum (FWHM).	
Side-mode suppression ratio	SMSR	-	Ratio of the intensity of the main mode to the intensity of the second strongest mode. Typically expressed in dBs.	Calculated from emission spectrum measured with spectrometer
Tuning range	Δv_{tun}	Hz	Range over which the emission frequency can be tuned	Spectrometer
Tuning type		-	Mode-hop-free or with mode hops	Spectrometer

5 Illumination systems

5.1 Overview

Historically, illumination systems represented the first use for artificial light sources, for example to illuminate some area during the night or in dark spots. There exist a plethora of illumination systems and applications from microscopic to giant scales. But the description of these is out of scope for this document. From a point of view of optoelectronic manufacturing, illumination systems based on LED and laser light sources are particularly interesting and we will therefore limit ourselves on those.

5.2 LED illumination systems

LED illuminators range from street lights to illumination for LCD screens down to miniature systems, like optical computer mice for example. LEDs are attractive light sources for many applications due to their efficiency (power to light conversion), abundant availability, low cost and flexibility. Indeed, LEDs are commercially available for emission wavelengths ranging from UV (275 nm) to several μm . They are area emitters with a surface typically $< 5 \text{ mm}^2$ and for illumination of large illumination surface or high power density many individual LEDs – identical or with distinct properties – are combined in arrays.

The functionality of such a system is to illuminate a given surface with light and it is characterized by the parameters:

- color
- luminance / brightness
- homogeneity across the illuminated surface (brightness and color)

These parameters are affected by environmental parameters that act either on the LED light sources or other components of the system (diffusers), or on both. These are:

- temperature, i.e. temperature sensitivity
- ageing effects [change of color (homogeneous or in-homogeneous), intensity / dimming]

5.2.1 Color

Color or the wavelength of the light emitted or reflected from the illuminated object, as it is perceived by the human eye, the sensor or the camera. By far the most LED illumination systems are based on white LEDs. White light can be produced by mixing the emission of three individual red, green and blue emitting LEDs. However, the field was revolutionized by the advent of blue emitting InGaN LEDs and the invention of phosphor-converted LEDs (pcLED). In this technology a blue emitting LED receives a coating of phosphor which converts the light to other wavelengths

by fluorescence. The mixture of these individual wavelengths will be perceived by the human eye as “white” and the color of the emitted light can be tuned by changing the dopants of the phosphor coating.

The emission wavelength of LEDs changes with junction temperature as well as through ageing. This effect is reduced with pcLEDs as the emission spectrum of the LED primarily depends on the phosphor coating and not on the underlying semiconductor.

5.2.2 Luminance / brightness

Luminance is a photometric measure of the luminous intensity per unit area of light travelling in a given direction and its SI unit is candela per square meter (cd/m^2). It describes the amount of light that passes through, is emitted from, or is reflected from a particular area, and falls within a given solid angle⁴.

5.2.3 Diffusers

In illumination systems a diffuser is a material that is placed between the light source(s) and the illuminated object and that renders the illumination pattern homogenous by diffusion or light scattering. Simple diffusers are composed of any translucent material like various glasses (ground, opal, greyed), PTFE or photopolymers. Photopolymers offer better performance than other materials and offer a large viewing angle and have been used for making holographic diffusers. However, being polymers they also are less stable and subject to ageing effects affecting their efficiency and durability.

5.3 LASER illumination systems

Laser devices are typically much more expensive than LEDs. Therefore, their use for illumination systems is limited to much more specific and highly technical applications. Examples are industrial machine vision, point projectors for 3D mapping of objects (face recognition in cell phones, etc.) and laser based displays or projectors.

In such systems the light source is typically one or several laser diodes (LD) or diode pumped solid state (DPSS) lasers. The emitted beam can be tailored with diffractive diffusers that are diffractive optical elements (DOE) that exploit the principles of diffraction and refraction. These elements use diffraction to manipulate monochromatic light, allowing to give the illumination beam a characteristic spatial configuration and intensity profile (typically flat-top). Spatial configurations can in principle be arbitrary but most often are squares, rectangles, circles, lines or arrays of these shapes are used.

The functionality of such systems is described by the following parameters:

- wavelength
- output shape and intensity profile (flat-top or customized)
- divergence angle or image size and EFL
- beam quality (M^2)

5.3.1 Speckles

When a surface is illuminated with spatially coherent light as from a laser, the diffuse reflections mutually interfere forming a speckle pattern. Even though this effect has been used in a variety of technical applications like microscopy (holographic interferometry), for all the display applications speckles are considered as a nuisance and several techniques exist to reduce the speckle contrast to a minimum: When several independent speckle patterns are superimposed they average-out on the detector or retina. This can be achieved by:

- angle diversity (illumination from different angles, each angle creating an independent set of speckles)

⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Luminance>

- polarization diversity
- wavelength diversity (for example multi-mode emission)

Commercial high-volume applications however (laser TV, ...) tend to use solutions where the spatial coherence of laser light is reduced. These include rotating diffusers and moving/vibrating screens and fibers⁵.

6 Imaging systems

6.1.1 Overview

An imaging system is a collection of optical elements (such as lenses or mirrors) which create an image on a specific plane from a (remote) object. Ideally, rays are emitted in all directions from a single point of the object and they converge on the image plane. There are a plenty of applications for an imaging system such as: visualize a distant object (telescope), visualize a small object (microscope), record an image (camera), or transfer an image of the environment to the brain (biological eye).

In this section, we describe first the relevant properties and components of an optical system (6.1.2). Secondly (6.1.3), we summarize how one can simulate an imaging system, thanks to ray tracing, as it is done by ray tracing software. Thirdly (6.1.4), we give the main mathematical properties of an imaging system that informs about the quality of it. Finally (6.1.5), we describe how one can measure the real performance of an imaging system, instead of simulating it.

6.1.2 Optical system

We define here the characteristic properties to define an optical system, which is particularly relevant for performing simulation on ray tracing software, such as OSLO[®] or Zemax[®].

First, the optical system is considered as a **collection of surfaces**. Each of which has several properties:

- **Number:** We label each surface with a number n , increasing from left to right. The surface on the right of the surface n is $n+1$ and the surface on the left is $n-1$.
- **Thickness:** the distance between the surface n and the surface $n+1$.
- **Size:** the diameter of the surface. Light can only pass through this diameter.
- **Radius of curvature:** There is no ambiguity for a spherical surface. If it is a flat surface, then the radius is infinity. If it is aspherical, we usually take the radius of curvature at the optical axis.
- **Surface shape function:** for a general case, we can define the position z of the surface as function of the x and y (or r in case of symmetry). The surface could be spherical, parabolic, elliptic, etc... One can use polynomial coefficients to define the surface function.
- **Refractive index:** on the right of the surface n . It can depend of the wavelength. In that case, we can use Sellmeier coefficients to calculate the refractive index for any wavelength.
- **Shift:** vertical or horizontal shift relative to the optical axis
- **Tilt:** angle of the surface with the optical axis.

⁵ Chellappan, Kishore V.; Erden, Erdem; Urey, Hakan (2010). "Laser-based displays: A review". *Applied Optics*. **49** (25): F79–98. [Bibcode:2010ApOpt..49F..79C](#). [doi:10.1364/ao.49.000f79](#). [PMID 20820205](#).

Then, one of the surfaces is defined as the **object**, another one as the **image plane** and another one as the **aperture** (this will affect the field angle and determine the pupil). Finally, one chooses one or several **wavelengths** for the rays that will go through the imaging system.

6.1.3 Simulation

We describe here how a simulation through ray tracing can be performed. The method is used with many softwares, but the physics is well known, and one can implement itself, if necessary.

- At first, the position and size of the **entrance and exit pupil** are calculated with a *paraxial approximation*. The entrance pupil is the image of the aperture through the surfaces positioned *before* the aperture, while the exit pupil is the image of the aperture through the surfaces positioned *after* the aperture.
- Then, the **ray tracing** is performed. This step usually takes most of the computing power. An ensemble of ray is picked. They all start from the object at optical axis, and their pointing direction is equally distributed on the entrance pupil, on a grid. The trajectory of each ray is calculated, as well as their optical path, by the use of the Snell equation. This requires calculation of the intersection of the ray with each surface (demanding part of the computing) and their relative angle with each surface. In the end, we obtain a collection of rays (**ray diagrams**), with their trajectory and their optical path at the intersection with the image plane.
- From the ray diagrams, we calculate the **wavefront aberration**. A wavefront is the set (locus) of all points where the wave has the same phase. The wavefront aberration is the optical path difference between a (spherical) perfect and real wavefront at every point on the exit pupil. Then, it might be convenient to decompose the wavefront aberration into Zernike polynomials, so that each Zernike coefficient correspond to a clear aberration, such as *defocus*, *coma* or *first order spherical aberration*.
- From the wavefront aberration, one calculates the **Point Spread Function (PSF)**. This is achieved by performing a 2D Fourier transform of the complex pupil plane function, which is the exponential of the wavefront aberration calculated above. The PSF simply corresponds to the image of a point on the image plane. Even without aberration, the points are “spread” because of the diffraction limit. The smaller is the aperture, the larger will be the spread.
- Finally, with a new Fourier transform of the PSF, one obtains the **optical transfer function (OTF)**. With this, one can predict the image of any object by simple multiplication in the Fourier plane.

6.1.4 Properties

Once the simulation is performed, we can use the results to describe the quality of the imaging system. We give here the main examples:

- as mentioned in the previous section, one can use the OTF to predict the image of any object. For example, we can simulate the **image of the letter E** and appreciate its readability.
- From the **Zernike coefficients** obtained from the wavefront aberrations, we have many ways of quantifying the quality of the image. One can focus on specific coefficients (defocus, coma), or one can calculate a single parameter from the all the Zernike coefficients. For example, the *RMS OPD* is the statistical optical path difference deviation average over the wavefront. Another example is the VSOTF, which is applied for human eye, and take into account the neurological response of the retina.
- A widely used parameter is the modulation transfer function **MTF**, which is the absolute value of the OTF. Often one gives the MTF for a specific spatial frequency. The interpretation is quite simple: it is the contrast (for a given spatial frequency) in the image. If

MTF=1, it means the imaging system can return a perfect contrast. However, the MTF is always limited by the diffraction limit, which decreases with increasing spatial frequency.

- The **Strehl ratio** is sometimes used. It is the ratio of the peak of the real PSF to the peak of an unaberrated PSF.

Moreover, one can re-compute any of the previous parameters by adding some defocus, which simulates object at different distances. With this, one can plot a *defocusing curve*, and it informs about a *depth-of-focus*. If it is large, it means one can obtain good image quality for objects at various distances.

6.1.5 Measurements

Once an imaging system is built, one can choose to measure directly the quality of it, with appropriate measurements. Compared to ray tracing simulation, it has the advantage to take into account the real system, including the imperfections. On the other hand, it might be more time-demanding, and the imperfections of the measurement itself can bias the result. We present here a few possible methods:

- the most direct method is to place an object (e.g. light source with a mask) and to appreciate the quality or readability of the image on a camera placed on the image plane. The object can be for example **a single letter**, or an US-air force target (USAF) which is often used as a reference.
- To measure directly the **MTF**, one could use a resolution target (alternating black and white lines) and measure the contrast on the image. However, one can only measure the MTF at the spatial frequency given by the target, and it is imperfect, as the object should consist of sinus waves instead of straight lines.
- In principle, one could measure directly the **PSF**, if the object is a point, i.e. a light source and pinhole. The main problem is that the pinhole must tend to be infinitely small, in which case there is no more light detected on the image plane.
- To solve this problem, one can use an **edge** of an object. The image will then correspond to the Edge Spread Function, from which we can compute the MTF, for any spatial frequency.
- Instead of a simple camera, one can use a **Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor** which measures directly the wavefront and the aberrations.
- Also, one can use any commercial **aberrometers**. Some of them use other designs than the Shack-Harmann, or some physical ray tracing method. These aberrometers can be more convenient to use and very powerful, but more costly and their design can be protected by a patent. Typically, they are used to characterize any lenses by a producer, or the visual performance of an human eye by an ophthalmologist.

In combination to these methods, it might be desirable to calculate a defocusing curve, i.e. simulate an object at various distances. To achieve this, one can add various lenses in front of the imaging system (*method of an ophthalmologist*), or place a lens on a rail to change its position to create a virtual object at any distance (*Badal optometer*).

7 Relevance to Use Cases

7.1 Alpes Lasers: CW single-mode DFB QCLs

Optical parameter	Related internal parameter	Acceptable range	Related fabrication steps
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Continuous-wave optical power	Thermal resistance Laser dimension	≥ 1 mW	Die bonding TEC soldering
Relative power stability	Thermal contact	$< 1\%$	Die bonding TEC soldering
Near field beam diameters	Lens position Waveguide width	< 3.5 mm	Lens alignment/attach Wafer processing (etching)
Far field beam divergence	Lens position Waveguide width	< 8 mRad	Lens alignment/attach Wafer processing (etching)
Beam waist diameters or spot size	Lens position Waveguide width	< 3.5 mm	Lens alignment/attach Wafer processing (etching)
Beam waist location	Lens position	< 20 cm from output window	Lens alignment/attach
Rayleigh range	Lens position Waveguide width	Wavelength dependent	Lens alignment/attach Wafer processing (etching)
Beam pointing error	Lens position	< 6 mRad	Lens alignment/attach
Beam pointing stability	Lens position fluctuations	< 1 mRad	Lens attach
Beam parameter product	Waveguide width	Wavelength dependent	Wafer processing (etching)
Beam propagation factor	Waveguide width	< 1.5	Wafer processing (etching)
Emission frequency	Grating period Effective refractive index	Application dependent	Wafer processing
Linewidth	Internal temperature stability	< 0.01 cm ⁻¹	Die bonding TEC soldering
Side-mode suppression ratio	Grating depth Position of facets with respect to grating	≥ 20 dB	Wafer processing Wafer cleaving
Tuning range	Thermal resistance	Application dependent	Die bonding TEC soldering
Tuning type	Grating depth Position of facets with respect to grating	Mode-hop free	Wafer processing Wafer cleaving

7.1.1 Grating period

First order DFB gratings for MIR wavelengths have grating periods in the range of 0.6 μ m to 1.8 μ m. Therefore, they can be fabricated by standard photolithography. Affordable photomasks have a minimal structure size of 0.3 μ m but we need a sub-nanometer resolution on the grating period in order to obtain the wavelength precision we require. Therefore, aliasing is used in order to obtain a “virtual” grating resolution of typically 0.5nm.

7.1.2 Waveguide width

We rely on wet-etching to fabricate the waveguide mesa for our standard products. Unfortunately, this step is not very well controlled and has typical mesa width uncertainty of $\pm 1\mu$ m (measured at wafer inspection stage after planar processing has been finished and wafer is received from fab). The tolerance allowed for our applications is typically in the order of $\pm 0.5\mu$ m. We therefore are required to perform waveguide-width bracketing strategies in order to ensure that we fabricate device with acceptable waveguide width – sacrificing global device yield.

7.1.3 Facet position

Spectral purity and side-mode suppression ratio depend on the phase between the DFB grating and the position of the front and back facet. This means that the position of the facet would have to be controlled with sub-micrometer precision, but in practice the precision we achieve with our manual scribing machine is in the order of $\pm 15\mu\text{m}$. This is a common problem for DFB lasers and therefore, mitigation strategies have been proposed, like implanting phase shifts in the grating or reducing the influence of the device facet by depositing anti-reflection coatings.

7.1.4 Collimation lens alignment

As the table above shows, the beam parameters for the device depend heavily on the positioning of the collimation lens. Currently, Alpes sub-contracts the mounting of the laser / lens assembly into a HHL package and therefore details regarding lens positioning are not known. Assembled HHL packages are controlled for external beam parameters (Poynting, divergence) and they need to fulfil the specs.

7.2 Prima Electro: Fiber-coupled high-power laser diode modules

Optical parameter	Related internal parameter	Acceptable range	Related fabrication steps
CoC: continuous-wave optical power	Active material quality	$\geq 8.5 \text{ W @ } 10 \text{ A}$ (Production Test Limit)	Epitaxial growth
CoC: continuous-wave optical power	Ridge definition Process control	$\geq 8.5 \text{ W @ } 10 \text{ A}$ (Production Test Limit)	Wafer Fab: semiconductor etch
CoC: continuous-wave optical power	Dielectric and metal layers	$\geq 8.5 \text{ W @ } 10 \text{ A}$ (Production Test Limit)	Wafer Fab: dielectric and metal deposition
CoC: diode voltage	Contact window quality	$< 2 \text{ V @ } 10 \text{ A}$ (Production Test Limit)	Wafer Fab: dielectric etch and metal depositions
CoC: continuous-wave optical power	Die attach quality (heat dissipation)	$\geq 8.5 \text{ W @ } 10 \text{ A}$ (Production Test Limit)	Back end: die attach
CoC: device Reliability	Die attach quality (heat dissipation)	Expected LifeTime compliance to product specs	Back end: die attach
CoC: device Reliability	Facet Quality according to visual inspection categories	Expected LifeTime compliance to product specs	Back end: scribing/coating/handling, detected at visual inspection
Module: continuous wave optical power	Lens alignments	$\geq 70 \text{ W @ } 10 \text{ A}$ (Production Test Limit)	Module optical assembly: lenses alignment/attach
Module: emitted spectrum	CoC soldering quality in module	$< 8 \text{ nm @ } 10 \text{ A}$	Module CoC assembly
Module: power drop during stress test	CoC failure	$< 5\% \text{ power drop @ } 10 \text{ A}$	Module CoC and optical assembly
Module: power drop during stress test	Optics failure	$< 5\% \text{ power drop @ } 10 \text{ A}$	Module optical assembly
Module: power drop during stress test	Fiber ferule failure	$< 5\% \text{ power drop @ } 10 \text{ A}$	Module optical assembly

7.2.1 Chip on Carrier (CoC) power and voltage fail

Emitted Power from CoC can be affected by many technological aspects, as reported in the above table: device not passing the product specs are rejected at testing department.

Epitaxial growth quality is the first crucial technological step affecting the power performances; every wafer growth batch is validated by a proper pilot wafer processing, which compliance to specification is carefully analyzed prior to enable the production on that particular batch.

Concerning the wafer fab processing, key technological steps are the ridge definition by the semiconductor chemical etch and the dielectric and metal layer depositions, also affecting the diode voltage drop at operating conditions.

7.2.2 Chip on Carrier (CoC) device reliability

Device reliability is defined by the product specification, and is assessed at Burn In level, which is screening out the weak part of the diode population. Each processed wafer is validated to be compliant to reliability product specs, and 100% of diodes are therefore screened by Burn In stress tests. Since also facet quality is strongly affecting the device reliability, a proper visual inspection stage is in place as well, to screen out any source of contamination.

7.2.3 Module power or spectrum fail

CoC pass at Burn In and visual inspection stages are good parts stored and used for multi-emitter module production. Power or spectrum fail at module level are detected by final tests and originated by not compliant CoC soldering quality in the package during module assembly, or not proper lens alignment during optical package step.

7.2.4 Module power fail (power drop) during stress test

Final test is also performing a stress test on 100% module production (typical stress is 100% max current for 12 hours). Power drop during stress test is detected by final test and module is rejected and routed to the recycle / rework steps. Defined root causes for power drops are: CoC failure, which trigger a CoC substitution or – according to product specs – short circuit; optics failure which involves optics rework; fiber ferule which trigger the ferule substitution and optics rework procedure.

7.3 HiLase / Filar: Disk lasers

Inappropriate bonding method of the active laser medium (in the form of thin disk of 100 to 200 μm thickness) to the heatsink, bad quality the bonding process, or insufficient quality of laser crystal surface polishing and coating can result in inhomogeneous mechanical and thermal contact between two materials. Voids and inhomogeneities in the contacting layers can influence temperature distribution of the bonded disk, create hotspots, and together with thermal expansion coefficient mismatch of the thin disk with epoxy and substrate layers causes irregular disk deformation or even delamination. This leads to drop of achievable output power, limited optical efficiency, and low stability of laser parameters. All those effects jointly deteriorate the quality of output laser beam and usability of the laser for applications.

Optical parameter	Related internal parameter	Related fabrication steps
Surface peak temperature	Thermal contact and its homogeneity:	Quality of material polishing (scratches and digs can cause voids)
Spatial temperature distribution	Peak temperature limits	

	<p>applicable pump and achievable output power. Irregular temperature distribution deteriorates beam quality through thermal lensing and asymmetric bending of thin disk</p>	<p>Quality and absorption of optical coatings (defects cause voids and hotspots)</p> <p>Homogeneity, viscosity and thermal conductivity of epoxies</p> <p>Technological steps and tools used in gluing procedure</p>
<p>Static radius of curvature of the disk (unpumped disk)</p>	<p>Epoxy layer quality and dimensions: Thickness and regularity of epoxy and other intermediate layers of the structure causes asymmetric bending of the disk</p>	<p>Gluing procedure – design of tools, timing of technological steps, epoxy viscosity</p> <p>Residual stress of optical coatings</p> <p>Flatness of thin disk and substrate (polishing quality)</p>
<p>Optical-to optical efficiency</p>	<p>Limits maximum laser output power, influencing required thickness and size of laser medium</p>	<p>The bonding method and thermomechanical properties of layers</p> <p>Design of gain medium efficiently suppressing amplified spontaneous emission (ASE), e.g. angle of polishing of edges, absorber layers, undoped parts</p>
<p>Pump-induced optical path difference</p>	<p>Dimensions and optomechanical properties of all layers: quantum defect and residual absorption and voids cause irregular temperature rise followed by asymmetric bending of thin disk by thermal expansion and thermal lensing of heated areas</p> <p>Quantum defect</p>	<p>Technology and quality of bonding layer</p> <p>Mismatch of thermomechanical parameters of layers</p> <p>Selection of pump radiation source can reduce quantum defect</p>
<p>M2</p>	<p>Quality of output beam is closely connected with spatial distribution of Optical Path Difference (the disk is bending)</p>	<p>Design of optical coatings</p> <p>Technology and quality of bonding layer</p> <p>Shape of the gain medium and the substrate</p> <p>Cavity alignment</p>

7.4 Brighterwave: Fiber-coupling assembly

Optical parameter	Related internal parameter	Related fabrication steps
Coupling efficiency	Laser dimensions Lens position(s) (distance(s) and alignment(s) with respect to the laser) Fiber position (distance and alignment with respect to the lens(es))	Laser fabrication Lens alignment/attach Fiber alignment/attach
Continuous-wave optical power	Laser dimensions / Thermal contact	Laser fabrication
Relative power stability		
Emission frequency		
Linewidth		
Side-mode suppression ratio		
Tuning range		
Tuning type		
Near field beam diameters	Laser dimensions / Lens position(s)	Laser fabrication / Lens alignment/attach
Far field beam divergence		
Beam waist diameters or spot size		
Beam waist location		
Rayleigh range		
Beam pointing error		
Beam pointing stability		
Beam parameter product		
Beam propagation factor		

7.4.1 Coupling efficiency

Coupling efficiency is highly dependent on the parameters numerical aperture and tapering listed in the section 2.2.1. These are properties of the fiber used in the setup.

7.4.2 Laser fabrication

Brighterwave designs and develops laser light sources, but laser fabrication is excluded from the scope of the Brighterwave's use case. Many parameters depend on the laser fabrication, but it is not specified here what particular fabrication step has an effect on the listed parameters.

8 Glossary

DOE: diffractive optical element

DPSS: diode-pumped solid-state

EFL: effective focal length

LASER: light amplification through stimulated emission of radiation

LCD: liquid crystal display

LED: light emitting diode

pcLED: phosphor-converted LED

